

Human Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells Proliferation and Secretion of Type I Interferon after Treatment with Polyherbal Formulations Fractions

Abubakar Usman¹, Kabir Hamid¹, Muawiya Abubakar¹, Ronaldson Achigbo¹, Hauwa Abdulrahman¹, Mohammed Yeldu², Umar Zulkfilu³, Mustapha Imam^{4,5}, Mansur Aliyu^{6*} , Nura Abubakar^{1,7}

¹Department of Immunology, School of Medical Laboratory Science, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

²Department of Chemical Pathology, School of Medical Laboratory Science, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

³Department of Internal Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Teaching Hospital, Sokoto, Nigeria.

⁴Center for Advance Medical Research and Training Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

⁵Department of Medical Biochemistry, College of Health Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

⁶Department of Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, Bayero University, P.M.B. 3011, Kano, Nigeria.

⁷Department of Health Services, Federal University Birnin Kebbi, P. M. B. 1157, Kebbi, Nigeria.

ARTICLE INFO

Corresponding Email. maliyu.med@buk.edu.ng

Received: 06-01-2023

Accepted: 27-01-2023

Published: 30-01-2023

Keywords. Human Immunodeficiency Virus, Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells, Polyherbal Formulations, Type I Interferons.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Background and aims. Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections are becoming resistant to therapy, despite extensive discoveries. The use of natural remedies for HIV treatment is becoming global. This study evaluates the in-vitro effect of aqueous extract of polyherbal formulation (PHF) fractions on peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) proliferation and secretion level of type I interferons. **Methods.** Column chromatography of the PHF yielded four fractions (A, B, C, and D). Different concentrations (25 µg/ml, 50 µg/ml, 100 µg/ml, and 200 µg/ml) of each fraction were prepared. A blood sample from a newly diagnosed HIV-positive volunteer was used. The percentage viability, cytotoxicity, and proliferation of the PBMCs were determined using the trypan blue dye exclusion method and WST-8 assay respectively. **Results.** The viability of the PBMC significantly decreased with increasing concentrations of each PHF fraction ($P=0.0001$). While fraction D exhibits the highest percentage of cytotoxicity, 16.17% at 200 g/ml, fraction C exhibits the lowest percentage of cytotoxicity at 25 g/ml concentration and upregulate interferons expression (IFN- α , IFN- β). Fractions A, B, and C induces significant PBMC proliferation ($P 0.0001$). **Conclusion.** The fractions have proliferative potential and enhance interferon production. In-depth PHF fractions and structural studies of the bioactive compounds are recommended.

Cite this article. Usman A, Hamid K, Abubakar M, Achigbo R, Abdulrahman H, Yeldu M, et al. Human Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells Proliferation and Secretion of Type I Interferon after Treatment with Polyherbal Formulations Fractions. *Alq J Med App Sci.* 2023;6(1):13-21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7582120>

INTRODUCTION

The use of plant compounds for pharmaceutical purposes has gradually increased [1], and according to the World Health Organization medicinal plants are probably the best source of a variety of drugs [2]. Plant-related pharmacological formulations are highly ranked for viral infections [3]. A variety of medicinal plants demonstrated a tremendous antiviral effect at various stages of viral growth [4]. The majority of the world's population uses herbs for the management of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) related symptoms [4]. Various medicinal plants are used in the treatment of HIV/AIDS such as *Withania somnifera* [5], *Tinospora cordifolia* [6], *Moringa oleifera* [7], *Hypericum perforatum* [8], *Silybum marianum* [4], and *Allium sativum* [9]. About 36.9 million people are living with HIV/AIDS (PLHIV) globally, with more than two-thirds living in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) [10]. Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), the advanced stage of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection is a major public health problem [11]. Due to the

high prevalence of HIV/AIDS and the emergence of drug-resistant strains, the demand for new antiviral drugs against AIDS is rising [12]. Management with antiviral agents is frequently yielding unsatisfactory clinical outcomes [13]. Refractory viral infections resistant to available antiviral drugs are alarming threats and serious health concerns [13]. Cytokines can be classified as pro and anti-inflammatory and are considered important initiators and mediators of inflammation [14]. Infection with HIV results in the production of cytokines by infected cells and cells of the immune system. Such cytokines regulate the immune function and affect viral replication [15]. Changes in cytokine levels in HIV-infected individuals can affect the function of the immune system and have the potential to directly impact the course of HIV disease by enhancing or suppressing HIV replication [16]. Immune deregulation during the development of AIDS is a result of cytokines imbalance. Cytokines that suppress HIV include interferon-alpha (IFN- α), interferon-beta (IFN- β), and interleukin 10 (IL-10) [15].

A lot of herbal medical practitioners in Nigeria, claim to have herbal formulations with immunomodulatory activities. The polyherbal formulation (PHF) used in this study contains five plant materials, which include the following: Black cutch- Bark (*Acacia polyacantha* wild), orchid bush-Bark (*Bauhinia rufescens* lam), Gum Arabic tree- Bark (*Acacia Senegal*), Baobab-leaves (*Adensonia digitata*), and Garlic-Yellow-bulb (*Allium sativum*). It is used by some people locally as a source of remedy for different diseases including HIV without prior knowledge of its adverse effects or which specific fraction of the formulation is responsible for the therapeutic effect. Previous studies on this PHF have reported improved neutrophil adhesion and T-dependent antibody response [17], immunostimulatory activity on murine Th1/Th2 cytokines secretion and cell-mediated immune response [18], and immunomodulatory activity on macrophage function and humoral immune response against sheep red blood cells in mice [19]. Indeed, a recent *in vivo* study shows it has protective potential in cyclophosphamide-induced immunosuppression [20]. This provides insight into its potential use in the management of immunocompromised conditions. However, the mechanistic bases of the *in vivo* effects are not well understood and the bioactive fractions of the PHF have not yet been studied. This study aims to identify the PHF fractions responsible for their therapeutic effect and to study their proliferative effect on the human PBMCs and cytokine secretions that are important in the suppression of viral replications. Therefore, it may pave the way for the production of a compound from a natural source for better treatment and/or management of immunocompromised conditions or viral infections. The study evaluates the *in-vitro* effects of fractions of PHF on the proliferation of PBMCs and the level of type-I interferons.

METHODS

Study design and setting

This is an *in vitro* study investigating the cytotoxic and or proliferative effect of polyherbal formulations fraction on human PBMCs of newly diagnosed HIV patient and secretion of type I interferons.

Polyherbal formulation

The polyherbal formulation consists of five plant materials namely: Black Cutch-Bark (*Acacia polyacantha* wild), Orchid Bush-Bark (*Bauhinia rufescens* lam), Gum Arabic tree-Bark (*Acacia Senegal*), Baobab-leaves (*Adensonia digitata*) and Garlic-Yellow-bulb (*Allium sativum*). The aqueous extract of the PHF was collected from the Department of Immunology, School of Medical Laboratory Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, which was initially stored and preserved at 5°C in airtight bottles and was labelled as PHF aqueous extracts. In stock preparation, 1 g of the PHF was dissolved in 10 ml of the distilled for 1 h at room temperature with gentle rocking at intervals to ensure complete and total dissolution of the PHF particles.

Thin layer chromatography

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was carried out at the Central Laboratory of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The fractions in the PHF were identified by using TLC, the technique used for the separation of non-volatile mixtures. The developing chamber was prepared by obtaining a jar that fits the entire TLC plate. Two 200 ml of the mixture ethanol/propanol/water/acetonitrile (1:1:1:1 V/V) was measured and 1 ml of the dissolved PHF in distilled water was added into the jar. The TLC plate was held next to the chamber to make sure that the solvent level is below the level of the spots. The TLC plate was inserted evenly into the chamber. The line and the spots are at the bottom of the plate and are above the level of the solvent. The chamber was covered with a lid. Once the solvent was close to the top of the plate, the plate was removed from the chamber, and the solvent line was marked with a pencil. The plate was allowed to dry and was then visualized under ultraviolet light.

Column chromatography

Column chromatography was carried out at the Central Laboratory of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Column chromatography was prepared and filled using cotton wool and fine sand (1.0 cm) while silica gel was used to pack the column for the stationary phase using a wet packing funnel. The mobile phase was poured into the column using a funnel. The column was gently tapped to remove air bubbles. Five millilitres (5 ml) of the dissolved PHF were loaded into the column, and four (4) different solvents were used to elude the PHF solution starting with the least polar i.e. propanol, methanol, distilled water, and acetonitrile. Fractions were collected from each solvent and were labelled fraction A, Fraction B, Fraction C, and Fraction D according to the solvent used to elute them mentioned above respectively. The collected fractions were again subjected to TLC to ascertain purity. Collected fractions were then transferred into a clean beaker and allowed to stand in a clean area to evaporate the excess solvent. After the evaporation fraction was then transferred into clean sterile cryovials and labelled Fractions A, B, C, and D. The cryovials were then stored at 5°C in a refrigerator.

Source of PBMCs

Three millilitres (3 ml) of whole blood was collected using the Monovette Vacutainer system containing lithium heparin as an anticoagulant from a 35-year-old volunteer who is diagnosed with HIV and has not commenced antiretroviral treatment. The patient gave his informed written consent to participate in the study which is to be published, having understood fully the research at hand. The sample was immediately transported to the Centre for Advanced Medical Research and Training (CAMRET), Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto for analysis. The study was conducted in accordance with the Helsinki declaration [21].

Isolation of PBMCs

The procedure for the isolation of the human PBMCs was carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions and also described previously [22]. Briefly, 3 ml of Histopaque-1077 (Sigma-Aldrich® Co. UK) was added to a 15 ml falcon tube and was brought to room temperature. Three milliliters (3 ml) of whole blood was layered onto the Histopaque-1077 carefully. Afterward, it was centrifuged at $400 \times g$ for 30 min at room temperature, the middle layer which contains the PBMCs was aspirated carefully with a Pasteur pipette to within 0.5 cm of the opaque interface containing mononuclear cells and was carefully transferred with a Pasteur pipette into a clean conical centrifuge tube. The cells were washed by adding 10 ml of isotonic phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution using a Pasteur pipette and were mixed by gently drawing in and out of a Pasteur pipette. The cells were washed by centrifugation at $250 \times g$ for 10 min and the supernatant was discarded. The cells pellets were suspended with 5 ml of isotonic PBS solution with a Pasteur pipette and were mixed by gently drawing in and out of the pipette. The cells were then centrifuged at $250 \times g$ for 10 min. The step was repeated two times, the cells pellets were resuspended in 2 ml of RPMI-1640 (Beijing Solar Bio Science and Technology Co. Ltd, China) and treated with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS).

Trypan blue assay

The procedure was carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions and described in [22]. Ten microliters (10 μ l) of 0.4% Trypan blue (Sigma-Aldrich® Co. UK) solution (w/v) and 10 μ l of the PBMCs suspension were transferred into a cryovials tube (dilution factor = 2) and mixed, it was then allowed to stand for a maximum of 5 min. While the coverslip was in place, the pipette was used to transfer 10 μ l of Trypan blue-PBMCs suspension mixture to both chambers of the haemocytometer. Both the viable and non-viable cells were counted using a light microscope. Non-viable cells are stained blue, whereas viable ones remain colourless. The percentage of viable cells was calculated.

Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity of the PHF fractions on PBMCs was determined using WST-8 cell proliferation assay kit (Beijing Solar bio Science and Technology Co. Ltd, China) and the procedure was carried out according to manufacturers' instructions. The cells (100 μ l/well) were seeded in 48-well microplate with RPMI-1640 medium at a concentration of 1×10^5 cells/well and incubated at 37°C and a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere incubator for 24 h. The cells in the 48-well microplate were then treated with different concentrations (25 μ g/ml, 50 μ g/ml, 100 μ g/ml, and 200 μ g/ml) of the PHF Fractions (A, B, C, D) at 10 μ l/well. The treated cells were then incubated for 4 h at 37°C and a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere incubator. After the incubation period, 10 μ l of WST-8 reagent was added to the treated cells and also the control. The cells were incubated for 1 h at 37°C and 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere incubator. The absorbance was read using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) microplate reader (Rayto-RT-2100C) at 450 nm and percentage cytotoxicity was calculated. All steps for the cytotoxicity test were done in duplicate as outlined by the manufacturer.

Proliferation assay

The proliferation of the PBMCs was determined according to the manufacturer's instructions. PBMCs suspension (100 μ l) was dispensed in 48-well microtiter plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells/well in RPMI-1640 at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ humidified incubator for 24h.

Phytohaemagglutinin (Sigma-Aldrich[®] Co. UK) (PHA: 10 μ g/ml) was added to each of the PBMCs cultures then 10 μ l /well of the PHF fractions (A, B, C, D) at 25 μ g/ml concentration (i.e. IC₅₀) was added. The cells were incubated for 4 h at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in a humidified atmosphere incubator. Then 10 μ l /well of WST-8 cell proliferation assay reagent (Beijing Solar bio Science and Technology Co. Ltd, China) was added and then incubated for 1 h at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in a humidified atmosphere incubator. PBMCs not treated with the extract, RPMI, FBS, and PBS were considered as controls. All treatments were performed in duplicate. The absorbance was read using an ELISA microplate reader (Rayto-RT-2100C) at 450 nm. The corrected absorbance is proportional to cell number (proliferation).

Levels of type I interferons

Cell culture supernatants were collected from the microtiter plate wells in clean cryovial tubes. It was centrifuged at 1000 x g for 10 min to remove debris and was assayed immediately for the cytokines level. The concentration of the interferons (IFN- α , IFN- β) was measured by quantitative sandwich ELISA technique (Beijing Solarbio Science & Technology Co., Ltd, China). The procedure was carried out with strict adherence to the manufacturer's instructional manual. The assay range for IFN- α and IFN- β was 10.90 pg/ml- 2500 pg/ml and 7.81 pg/ml–500 pg/ml respectively. The assay sensitivity for IFN- α and IFN- β was 20.0 pg/ml and 4.0 pg/ml respectively.

Statistical analysis

The results obtained were entered into SPSS version 25 (IBM, USA) for analysis. Continuous variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD), whereas categorical variables were expressed in percentages. One-way between-groups analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a post hoc test (Bonferroni) was carried out to compare between groups. Independent sample t-test was carried out to compare the mean absorbance of control and treatment on the level of type-I interferons. The $P \leq 0.05$ was used to determine the level of statistical significance.

RESULTS

PHF fractions

The PHF when subjected to Thin Layer Chromatography and Column Chromatography yielded four different fractions according to the type of solvent used in the separation, the fractions extracted were named Fractions A, B, C, and D according to the sequence of collection, fraction A was collected from propanol, fraction B was collected from methanol, fraction C was collected from water and fraction D was collected from acetonitrile.

PBMCs count and percentage viability

The total viable cell count of the isolated PBMCs was 1944×10^4 cells/ml while the non-viable total cell count was 80×10^4 cells/ml. The percentage of PBMC viability was found to be 96.05%.

Determination of percentage cytotoxicity of the PHF fractions on PBMCs

The minimum inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of each of the four fractions was determined using different concentrations of the fractions A, B, C, and D (25 μ g/ml, 50 μ g/ml, 100 μ g/ml, and 200 μ g/ml). The concentrations of each of the fractions at 25 μ g/ml had the lowest mean percentage cytotoxicity: Fraction A (0.39%), Fraction B (0.43%), Fraction C (0.28%), and Fraction D (2.43%), whereas the concentration of each fraction at 200 μ g/ml had the highest mean percentage cytotoxicity: Fraction A (10.51%), Fraction B (13.59%), Fraction C (6.59%), and Fraction D (16.17%). Therefore, the minimum concentration with the lowest cytotoxicity was 25 μ g/ml concentration of each fraction (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Mean percentage Cytotoxicity of each of the fraction on the PBMCs. The cytotoxicity increased with an increase in concentrations. Fraction C at 25 µg/ml shows the least cytotoxicity on the PBMCs. Whereas Fraction D displayed the highest cytotoxicity at 25 µg/ml.

Effect of different concentrations of PHF fractions on the PBMCs

A one-way between-groups analysis of variance was conducted to explore the effect of an aqueous extract of PHF fractions on PBMCs. As depicted in figure 2, there was a difference in PBMC mean absorbance scores across the different concentrations of the PHF fractions ($P < 0.0001$).

Figure 2: Effect of different concentrations of PHF fractions on the PBMCs. The mean absorbance decreased with an increase in fraction concentrations. Post-hoc comparison shows that all the fractions at 100 and 200 concentrations significantly differ from control. Absorbance is directly proportional to the number of viable cells. a; control vs 100 µg/ml, b; 25 µg/ml vs 100 µg/ml, c; 50 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, d; control vs 100 µg/ml, e; 25 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, f; control vs 200 µg/ml, g; 25 µg/ml vs 100 µg/ml, h; 50 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, i; control vs 100 µg/ml, j; 25 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, k; control vs 200 µg/ml, l; 25 µg/ml vs 100 µg/ml, m; 50 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, n; control vs 100 µg/ml, o; 25 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, p; control vs 200 µg/ml, q; 25 µg/ml vs 100 µg/ml, r; 50 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml, s; control vs 100 µg/ml, t; 25 µg/ml vs 200 µg/ml. * $P = 0.05$, ** $P = 0.008$, * $P < 0.0001$. A= fraction A, B= fraction B, C= fraction C, D= fraction D**

Effect of different PHF fractions on the proliferation of PBMCs

A one-way between-groups analysis of variance was conducted to explore the effect of aqueous extract of the PHF fractions at 25 µg/ml on the proliferation of PBMCs. As depicted in figure 3, there was significant difference in PBMCs mean absorbance scores across the different fractions of the PHF and control ($P < 0.0001$).

Figure 3: Effect of Different PHF Fractions on Proliferation of PBMCs. Post-hoc comparisons using the Bonferroni test indicated that there was significant difference in the mean absorbance scores for the proliferation of control PBMCs when compared with the different fractions; A, B, C, and D. So also when fraction C was compared with other fractions, there was significant difference. Absorbance is directly proportional to cellular proliferation. a; control vs fractions A ($P < 0.0001$), b; control vs fraction B ($P < 0.0001$), c; control vs fraction C ($P < 0.0001$), d; control vs fraction D ($P < 0.0001$). *** $P < 0.0001$

Effect of PHF fraction C on the level of type -I interferon

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare the mean concentration of supernatant IFN- α and IFN- β secreted by PBMCs for treatment and control after treatment with 25 µg/ml (IC₅₀) concentration of fraction C. There was significant difference between the treatment mean concentration of the cytokines (IFN- α , IFN- β) and control ($P < 0.0001$) (figure 4).

Figure 4: Effect of Fraction C on the Level of Type-I Interferons. The secretion of the cytokines was significantly increased compared with that of control after treatment of PBMCs with 25 µg/ml of fraction C.

DISCUSSION

Medicinal plants' acceptability for the treatment of pathological conditions is increasing worldwide [23]. So much research is needed to identify the untapped therapeutic potential of the plant's material [24]. For safety purpose, thorough investigations are required on any plant compound aimed for therapeutic use [25]. The percentage cytotoxicity on PBMCs in this study significantly increases with an increase in the concentration of the studied PHF. Cytotoxic

compounds are toxic to cells as they induce undesirable necrosis or apoptosis [26]. We reported 0.28% as the least percentage of cytotoxicity from fraction C at 25 µg/ml concentration. This activity may be attributed to differences in the bioactive component between fraction C and other fractions. However, the lowest concentration (0.0625 mg/ml) of *Commiphora kerstingii* leaves extract exhibit cellular growth inhibition of 52.85% [27]. Some constituents of medicinal plants are potentially toxic [28], as such are not free from toxic effects [29].

This study demonstrated that the PHF fractions have significant immune-proliferative activity on the PBMCs at 25 µg/ml concentration. This suggests the fractions induce cell division among the PBMCs. Absorbance is directly proportional to the concentration of the PBMCs. The differences in absorbance scores may be a result of the variation in bioactive compounds present in the respective fractions, with fraction C containing the bioactive compound responsible for the high proliferative activity. Indeed, the mean absorbance of fractions A, B, and C is reasonably higher than that of the control suggesting the presence of the stimulatory compounds responsible for the said activity. However, fraction D has a lower mean absorbance score compared with the control suggesting low immune-proliferative activity. Cellular proliferation refers to an increase in cell number due to cell division (cytokinesis), this occurs at the final step of the cell cycle. Healthy cells actively proliferate, whereas growth-arrested, senescent, and dead or dying cells do not [30]. *Rhaphidophora korthalsii* methanol extract was shown to stimulate PBMCs proliferation and maintain their viability [31]. Suberosin isolated from *Plumbago zeylanica* has a profound inhibitory effect on the activation and proliferation of human PBMCs stimulated with PHA [32]. Crude extract from the leaf of *Albizia gumifera* inhibits the proliferation of mononuclear cells in a dose-dependent manner [33].

Fraction C of the PHF studied here has the least cytotoxic effect coupled with the highest proliferative activity on the PBMCs, hence selected to be studied for cytokine secretion. Herein, we reported significant upregulation of IFN- α and IFN- β secretions compared with the control, which suggests that the fraction has compound(s) that can induce the secretion of type I cytokines. The same crude extract of the PHF induced the secretion of Th1/Th2 cytokines such as IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, and IFN- γ *in vivo* [18]. IFN- α and IFN- β are both secreted by immune and non-immune cells in response to a viral infection [34,35], with both anti-viral and immunomodulatory activities on target cells [36]. The application of these cytokines in the treatment of viral infection is remarkable [37]. For instance, in the treatment of hepatitis B and C viral infections [38].

Innate cytokine responses, particularly type I interferon, play an important role in coordinating the entire immune reaction to HIV and other pathogenic organisms, and have direct impacts on T cells, altering their functional properties. Understanding these multifaceted cytokine interactions may aid in the identification of valuable drug targets for therapeutics or vaccines [39]. IFN- α provides a therapeutic intervention target for viral infection, able to suppress HIV replication, but not expressed at higher levels in chronic HIV infection due to depletion of their rich source-plasmacytoid DCs (pDC). IFN- α potentiates cell mediated immunity that is deficient in HIV infection [39]. Infection of monocyte/macrophages by HIV induces secretion of IFN- β , which in turn restricts viral replication through blockade of p24 release [40]. Transduction of IFN- β into dendritic cells resulted in resistance to HIV infection and inhibition of HIV transmission [41].

CONCLUSION

Despite extensive research and the discovery of an array of pharmacological agents, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections are becoming refractory to therapy. The use of herbal products for the treatment of HIV is growing in popularity worldwide. Type I interferons were shown to play an important defensive role in viral infections. This study demonstrated significant proliferative activity of Fraction A, B, and C on PBMCs. It revealed significant increase in IFN- α and IFN- β levels induced by selected Fraction C. These activities indicate the fractions possess compound(s) that potentiate the expression of type-I cytokines. Therefore, an in-depth research on the effect of the PHF fractions on individual cells of the PBMCs will provide useful data for therapeutics, also structural analysis to identify the structure of the compound responsible for the bioactivity.

Authors' contribution

Conceptualization and study design UAB, HKM, YMH, IMU, AMa, and AMu. Experiments and data acquisition: UAB, HKM, YMH, ZU, ARA, AHM and ANK. Data analysis and interpretation: HKM, UAB, AMa, ZU, ARA and IMU. Manuscript drafting and literature search: UAB, HKM, IMU, AMu, YMH, AHM, ANK and AMa. All authors critically revised the manuscript and approved the final version for submission.

Acknowledgement

We sincerely appreciate the contribution of Mr. Sani Muhammad Umar (Nagge) of Al Mustakshif Medical Health Centre, Kano, Nigeria (RC: 1393615) for the Garjin® PHF.

Funding. This research received no funding

Disclaimer

The article has not been previously presented or published.

Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

REFERENCES

- Bamidele F, Ogundipe F, Shogeyinbo U. Determination of antibacterial activity and phytochemistry of three herbal plants on clinical isolates. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. 2014;39(12):23-9.
- Ellof J. Which extract should be used for the screening and isolation of antimicrobial components from plants? *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 1998;60(1):1-8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741\(97\)00123-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741(97)00123-2)
- Newman DJ, Cragg GM. Natural products as sources of new drugs over the 30 years from 1981 to 2010. *Journal of Natural Products*. 2012;75(3):311-35. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np200906s>
- Lovelace ES, Maurice NJ, Miller HW, Slichter CK, Harrington R, Magaret A, et al. Silymarin suppresses basal and stimulus-induced activation, exhaustion, differentiation, and inflammatory markers in primary human immune cells. *PloS One*. 2017;12(2):e0171139. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0171139>
- Williams-Orlando C. Human immunodeficiency virus and herbal medicine. *Alternative Complementary Therapies*. 2017;23(2):51-9. <https://doi.org/10.1089/act.2017.29099.cwo>
- Husain A, Kaushik A, Awasthi H, Singh DP, Khan R, Mani D. Immunomodulatory and antioxidant activities of fresh juice extracts of Brahmi and Guduchi. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*. 2017;16(3):498-505.
- Monera-Penduka TG, Maponga CC, Wolfe AR, Wiesner L, Morse GD, Nhachi CF. Effect of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. leaf powder on the pharmacokinetics of nevirapine in HIV-infected adults: a one sequence cross-over study. *AIDS Research and Therapy*. 2017;14(1):1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12981-017-0140-4>
- Béjaoui A, Ben Salem I, Rokbeni N, M'rabet Y, Boussaid M, Boulila A. Bioactive compounds from *Hypericum humifusum* and *Hypericum perforatum*: inhibition potential of polyphenols with acetylcholinesterase and key enzymes linked to type-2 diabetes. *Pharmaceutical Biology*. 2017;55(1):906-11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13880209.2016.1270973>
- Maroyi A. Alternative medicines for HIV/AIDS in resource-poor settings: Insight from traditional medicines use in sub-Saharan Africa. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2014;13(9):1527-36. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v13i9.21>
- Anywar G, Kakudidi E, Byamukama R, Mukonzo J, Schubert A, Oryem-Origa H. Indigenous traditional knowledge of medicinal plants used by herbalists in treating opportunistic infections among people living with HIV/AIDS in Uganda. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2020;246:112205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2019.112205>
- Poteat T, Scheim A, Xavier J, Reisner S, Baral S. Global epidemiology of HIV infection and related syndemics affecting transgender people. *Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*. 2016;72(Suppl 3):S210. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAI.0000000000001087>
- Wilson D, Goggin K, Williams K, Gerkovich MM, Gqaleni N, Syce J, et al. Consumption of *Sutherlandia frutescens* by HIV-seropositive South African adults: an adaptive double-blind randomized placebo controlled trial. *PloS One*. 2015;10(7):e0128522. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0128522>
- Akram M, Tahir IM, Shah SMA, Mahmood Z, Altaf A, Ahmad K, et al. Antiviral potential of medicinal plants against HIV, HSV, influenza, hepatitis, and coxsackievirus: A systematic review. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2018;32(5):811-22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.6024>
- Dinareello CA. Proinflammatory cytokines. *Chest*. 2000;118(2):503-8. <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.118.2.503>
- Ramana K. Effect of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) on human immunodeficiency virus disease pathogenesis and progression. *American Journal of Public Health Reserch*. 2014;2(3):68-74. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajphr-2-3-1>
- Breen EC. Pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in human immunodeficiency virus infection and acquired immunodeficiency syndrome. *Pharmacology & therapeutics*. 2002;95(3):295-304. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-7258\(02\)00263-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-7258(02)00263-2)
- Yahaya IS, Yeldu MH, Hamid KM, Musa U, Kalgo MU. Effect of polyherbal formulation on neutrophil function and TDAR in Wistar albino rat. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*. 2018;5(12):563-8.
- Hamid KM, Isah SY, Kalgo MU, Isiyaku A, Usman AB, Yeldu MH, et al. Immunostimulatory ctivity of Aqueous Extract of Polyherbal Formulation on Th1/Th2 Cytokines Secretion and Cell Mediated Immune Response in Rats. *Saudi Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2021;10:11.
- Hamid KM, Shehu AA, Kalgo MU, Isiyaku A, Alkali S, Muhammad T, et al. Immunomodulatory activity of aqueous extract of polyherbal formulation on macrophage function and humoral immune response against SRBCs in mice. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Science*. 2021;34(2):3989-97. <https://doi.org/10.48198/NJPAS/21.A01>
- Abubakar NK, Hamid KM, Yeldu MH, Abdullahi MI, Usman AB, Isah SY, et al. Protective activity of a polyherbal formulation in cyclophosphamide-induced immunosuppression. *Ethiopian Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2021;37:33-44. <https://doi.org/10.4314/epj.v37i1.3>
- Rickham PP. Human experimentation. Code of ethics of the world medical association. Declaration of Helsinki. *British Medical Journal*. 1964;2(5402):177. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.2.5402.177>

22. Hamid KM, Yakubu A, Sani SA, Kalgo MU, Isiyaku A, Umahi NPF, et al. Immunocytotoxic effect of aqueous leaf extract of *Cassia occidentalis* on human peripheral blood mononuclear cells and neutrophils. *UMYU Journal of Microbiology Research*. 2021;6(2):30-6. <https://doi.org/10.47430/ujmr.2162.005>
23. Ishii R, Yoshikawa K, Minakata H, Komura H, Kada T. Specificities of bio-antimutagens in plant kingdom. *Agricultural and Biological Chemistry*. 1984;48(10):2587-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00021369.1984.10866552>
24. Graça VC, Barros L, Calhella RC, Dias MI, Ferreira IC, Santos P. Bio-guided fractionation of extracts of *Geranium robertianum* L.: Relationship between phenolic profile and biological activity. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 2017;108:543-52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.07.016>
25. Teixeira RdO, Camparoto ML, Mantovani MS, Vicentini VEP. Assessment of two medicinal plants, *Psidium guajava* L. and *Achillea millefolium* L., in *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. *Genetics and Molecular Biology*. 2003;26(4):551-5. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1415-47572003000400021>
26. Niles AL, Moravec RA, Eric Hesselberth P, Scurria MA, Daily WJ, Riss TL. A homogeneous assay to measure live and dead cells in the same sample by detecting different protease markers. *Analytical Biochemistry*. 2007;366(2):197-206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ab.2007.04.007>
27. Khan M. Phytochemical screening, antioxidant and antibacterial Activities of *Commiphora kerstingii*. *International Biological and Biomedical Journal Summer*. 2016;2:27-32.
28. Akintonwa A, Awodele O, Afolayan G, Coker HAB. Mutagenic screening of some commonly used medicinal plants in Nigeria. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2009;125(3):461-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2009.07.013>
29. Edziri H, Mastouri M, Mahjoub A, Anthonissen R, Mertens B, Cammaerts S, et al. Toxic and mutagenic properties of extracts from Tunisian traditional medicinal plants investigated by the neutral red uptake, VITOTOX and alkaline comet assays. *South African Journal of Botany*. 2011;77(3):703-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2011.03.007>
30. Kumar D, Arya V, Kaur R, Bhat ZA, Gupta VK, Kumar V. A review of immunomodulators in the Indian traditional health care system. *Journal of Microbiology, Immunology and Infection*. 2012;45(3):165-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmii.2011.09.030>
31. Swee KY, Noorjahan BMA, Wan YH, Abdul RO, Abdul MA, Boon KB, et al. Immunomodulatory role of *Rhaphidophora korthalsii* methanol extract on human peripheral blood mononuclear cell proliferation, cytokine secretion and cytolytic activity. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*. 2011;5(6):958-65.
32. Chen YC, Tsai WJ, Wu MH, Lin LC, Kuo YC. Suberosin inhibits proliferation of human peripheral blood mononuclear cells through the modulation of the transcription factors NF-AT and NF- κ B. *British Journal of Pharmacology and Toxicology*. 2007;150(3):298-312. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bjp.0706987>
33. Makgatho ME, Mashele SA, Makhubele TG, Sedibane ML, Bagla VP, Mashinya F, et al. *In vitro* immune-modulatory potential of crude extract of leaf of *Albizia gummifera* against stimulated peripheral blood mononuclear and raw cells. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*. 2015;12(3):85-90. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajtcam.v12i3.10>
34. Gharavi M, Nobakht M, Khademvatan S, Bandani E, Bakhshayesh M, Roozbehani M. The effect of garlic extract on expression of INF γ and inos genes in macrophages infected with *Leishmania major*. *Iranian Journal of Parasitology*. 2011;6(3):74.
35. Bolívar S, Anfossi R, Humeres C, Vivar R, Boza P, Muñoz C, et al. IFN- β plays both pro- and anti-inflammatory roles in the rat cardiac fibroblast through differential STAT protein activation. *Front Pharmacol*. 2018;9:1368. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2018.01368>
36. Hirahara K, Nakayama T. CD4⁺ T-cell subsets in inflammatory diseases: beyond the T_H1/T_H2 paradigm. *International Immunology*. 2016;28(4):163-71. <https://doi.org/10.1093/intimm/dxw006>
37. Gholijani N, Gharagozloo M, Kalantar F, Ramezani A, Amirghofran Z. Modulation of cytokine production and transcription factors activities in human Jurkat T cells by thymol and carvacrol. *Advanced Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2015;5(Suppl 1):653. <https://doi.org/10.15171/apb.2015.089>
38. Gao Q-J, Liu D-W, Zhang S-Y, Jia M, Wang L-M, Wu L-H, et al. Polymorphisms of some cytokines and chronic hepatitis B and C virus infection. *World Journal of Gastroenterology*. 2009;15(44):5610. <https://doi.org/10.3748/wjg.15.5610>
39. Reuter MA, Pombo C, Betts MR. Cytokine production and dysregulation in HIV pathogenesis: lessons for development of therapeutics and vaccines. *Cytokine and Growth Factor Reviews*. 2012;23(4-5):181-91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cytogfr.2012.05.005>
40. Gessani S, Puddu P, Varano B, Borghi P, Conti L, Fantuzzi L, Belardelli F. Induction of beta interferon by human immunodeficiency virus type 1 and its gp120 protein in human monocytes-macrophages: role of beta interferon in restriction of virus replication. *J Virol*. 1994;68(3): 1983-6. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jvi.68.3.1983-1986.1994>
41. Cremer I, Vieillard V, Sautès-Fridman C, De Maeyer E. Inhibition of Human Immunodeficiency Virus Transmission to CD4⁺ T Cells after Gene Transfer of Constitutively Expressed Interferon β to Dendritic Cells. *Human Gene Therapy*. 2000;11(12): 1695-703. <https://doi.org/10.1089/10430340050111340>